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Copolymeric membranes of heteropolyacid embedded poly (vinyl alcohol)-g-acrylamide and their evaluation for proton exchange membrane fuel cells

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Introduction: The development of purposeful fuel cells trace back in the early 1800's by Sir William Grove and who become considered as discoverer of fuel cell in 1839. After attaining this great achievement scientists across the globe have been attempted to develop fuel cell technology by various electrolytes and fuels. In the early 20th century first time fuel cell systems are used in Gemini and Apollo space flights. In the year 1959 first time the fully operated new generation fuel cell was demonstrated by Francis T. Bacon successfully. Later in the year 1960 proton exchange membrane fuel cell was developed and used by NASA as part of Gemini space program and the mission successfully continued for seven of its mission.

Methods: *Synthesis of Copolymer:* 5 g of PVA was dissolved in water at 60°C. Adequate amount of acrylamide (1 g) and initiator (0.4 wt.% to comonomer) were introduced to reaction vessel under continuous stirring. The temperature was maintained at 80°C for 6 Hrs. The obtained reaction mixture was precipitated in methanol and filtered under vacuum. The obtained product was dried in vacuum oven at 60°C for 12 Hrs.

Na-tungstate embedded copolymeric membrane fabrication and crosslinking: The synthesized PVA-g-AAm copolymer was dissolved in 100 mL of distilled water at 60°C. Once the viscous slurry was obtained different gravimetric ratio of Na-Tungstate (i.e. 1, 2.5 and 5 wt.% w.r.t total copolymeric weight) were added as filler under continuous stirring. The solution was cast on to doctor's a neat and clean glass plate with the help of blade. The casted solution was allowed to dry under dust free atmosphere. Once the solution was dried membrane was peeled off from the glass plate and stored properly. Further the membranes were crosslinked with glutaraldehyde by soaking them in a crosslinking bath containing 5 mL of glutaraldehyde.

Results & Discussions: Ion exchange capacity test was performed for the crosslinked PVA-g-AAm copolymer and compared with uncrosslinked membrane. The uncrosslinked PVA-g-AAm showed 2.108 meq/g and the crosslinked PVA-g-AAm showed IEC of 0.593 meq/g. The IEC, which is equal to the total number of free hydroxyl and amide groups, has decreased after crosslinking reaction. The results shows that approximately 72% of the hydroxyl and amide groups from the uncrosslinked copolymeric membrane have involved in the crosslinking reaction with glutaraldehyde. However, there are still some extra hydroxyl and amide groups are present and they allow the diffusion of molecules through crosslinked copolymeric membrane. The proton conductivity plots have been obtained shown in Figure 1. The obtained data shown that the modified membranes showed better performance as compared to its plain membrane. The plain membrane showed $3.492 \times 10^{-2} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ for 75 % RH to $3.942 \times 10^{-2} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$. Whereas 5 wt.% Na-Tungstate loaded Membranes showed 6.315 to $13.333 \times 10^{-2} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ for 75% to 100% RH.

Figure 1. Proton conductivity curves for the different Na-Tungstate loaded membranes.

Keywords: Fuel cell, copolymer, grafting reaction, proton exchange

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